

QUIZ**LAST NAME: VICTORIA****FIRST NAME: OGBUEHI****PROGRAM CODE: DTCD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: P6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. When directly quoting a piece of text...

- You should reproduce the original¹.**
- You must never alter the original text without indicating it.
- You should try as much as possible to alter the original text.
- You may not use the quotation marks provided the quote is verbatim.

2. In a list of three or more items, a comma is used to separate them except for the final two, which are separated by 'and' or 'or'²

1. European Commission. English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission. Seventh edition (Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 7

2. European Commission, 9.

- True**
- False
- Sometimes
- The comma is used from the beginning to the end irrespective of the number of items on the list

3 Applying All but one of these options will guide a writer from committing inadvertent plagiarism

- You can plead ignorance if need be since it was an innocent mistake³**
- Don't plead ignorance
- Don't paraphrase too closely
- Signal every quotation even when you have cited its source

4 One of the most important tasks of a Doctoral student is

- Finding a suitable advisement team⁴**
- Mastering the art of writing
- Avoiding plagiarism at all cost
- Completing courses within the stipulated timeline

3 Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 52.

4 Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 16.

5 Why is it important to state the significance of the research questions?

- It helps to answer the question of ‘so what’ or ‘then answer it’ by the readers⁵**
- It is proof that the writer is an expert
- Doing that earns the writer more marks.
- Because of the need to clarify the choices of your questions to the readers.

6 In citing a British government document, you must

- End citations with the phrase the United Kingdom (in parentheses or brackets) unless it is obvious from the context.⁶**
- You must compare the document with what is obtainable in the United States of America.
- Not use comma more than once.
- You must use the case title.

7 The following are examples of well-used hyphens except

- All of the options.⁷**
- A two-day meeting.
- Product-by-product input-output tables.
- A four-month stay (but four months’ holiday).

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 71.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 160.

⁷ Ibid.

8 Your dissertation is a project that

- Will extend over a while.⁸**
- Its completion is dependent on the availability of a supervisor.
- That shouldn't take more than 12 months to complete.
- You should undertake it at your own pace.

9 Responsible researchers are

- A Don't repeat quotations that they have not seen in the original.⁹**
- Intelligent.
- Curious.
- Open-minded.

10 The starting point for any research project, and indeed the first major challenge in conducting a research is.

- Coming to some decision about a sound and a doable topic.¹⁰**
- Scheduling your time using the MS project software.
- Interfacing with participants to better understand their problems.
- Researching a topic that is difficult but in great demand

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 71.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, 161.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 5.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation- A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. First edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Inc., 2008.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide : A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Seventh edition. Directorate-General for Translation, 2011.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.